

higher photosynthetic rate. Between the two rice cultivars, IET1444 had better growth in the upland than Nipponbare; however, it was not associated with photosynthetic response.

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Evaluation of stand establishment techniques in lowland irrigated rice

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Transplanting of rice seedlings is an age-old practice. In recent years, the migration of labor to the industrial sector, especially in India, has led to the nonavailability of labor for transplanting at the appropriate time, resulting in a yield reduction. This method of stand establishment is also laborious and time-consuming and results in drudgery among women workers. Cultivation practices, such as nursery preparation and management, fertilizer and pesticide application and irrigation to the nursery, pulling out seedlings, and transplanting in the main field, account for the major share of cultivation costs. Hence, an alternative method had to be found to overcome problems encountered in using the transplanting technique.

Direct seeding and throwing of seedlings under puddled conditions are viable alternatives to transplanting. Matsushima (1980) cited the advantages of throwing seedlings over a puddled field instead of transplanting. Hence, a study was conducted to evaluate the feasibility of different stand establishment techniques in lowland irrigated rice during the 1999 wet season

(Aug-Dec) and 2000 dry season (Feb-May).

Four stand establishment techniques—transplanting (T_1), seedling throwing (T_2), direct seeding by manual broadcasting (T_3), and wet seeding by a drum seeder (T_4)—were tested in a randomized block design with five replications. The test variety was ADT43 (110 d) and the recommended dose of NPK (125:50:50 kg ha⁻¹) was applied. In transplanting, the recommended 15 × 10-cm spacing was adopted. Seedling throwing consisted of separating two or three seedlings, as is done during normal transplanting, and randomly throwing them in a standing position on a puddled and leveled field to maintain the same plant density per unit area. Twenty-day-old seedlings were used for transplanting and seedling throwing. Seeding rates of 80 and 100 kg ha⁻¹ were used for drum seeding and manual broadcasting, respectively. Sprouted seeds were used for direct seeding. The eight-row drum seeder used in this trial was developed by TNAU's Department of Agricultural Engineering.

The various stand establishment techniques—direct (wet)

seeding by manual broadcasting or a drum seeder or transplanting—showed no significant difference in grain yield in both seasons (see table). In a pooled analysis of two seasons, grain yield was highest in wet seeding by manual broadcasting, closely followed by direct seeding using a drum seeder and traditional transplanting. A similar trend was observed in straw yield. Although wet seeding by manual broadcasting and drum seeding had no significant difference in grain yield, intercultural operations, such as weeding and spraying, could be easily adopted in wet seeding by a drum seeder since there is a definite row arrangement. In both wet-seeding practices and seedling throwing, the cultivation cost was less than with transplanting; less labor cost translated into an increase in income. In both seasons, the net income and benefit-cost ratio were highest in wet seeding by manual broadcasting, closely followed by wet seeding by a drum seeder. Using wet seeding by manual broadcasting and a drum seeder could result in a higher net income and benefit-cost ratio than traditional transplanting. Both direct-seeding

Effect of stand establishment techniques on yield and economics of lowland irrigated rice.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Days to 50% flowering		Net income (Rs ha ⁻¹) ^a			Benefit-cost ratio		
	Wet	Dry	Mean	Wet	Dry	Mean	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Mean	Wet	Dry	Mean
T ₁ Transplanting	6.0	5.2	5.6	9.6	7.5	8.6	85.6	78.6	18,666	12,984	15,825	2.10	1.76	1.93
T ₂ Seedling throwing	4.9	4.7	4.8	8.1	6.9	7.5	85.2	79.0	14,853	12,605	13,732	2.01	1.86	1.93
T ₃ Wet seeding: broadcasting manually	6.1	5.3	5.7	9.3	7.6	8.4	76.8	73.0	21,551	16,529	19,039	2.51	2.16	2.33 ^b
T ₄ Wet seeding: drum seeder	6.1	5.3	5.6	9.1	7.5	8.3	76.8	72.8	21,214	15,959	18,587	2.48	2.11	2.29 ^b
CD at 5%	0.13	0.13	0.11	0.53	0.55	0.11	2.0	1.7	na	na	na	na	na	na

^aUS\$1 = Rs 46. ^bAdditional seed cost also included. na = not applicable.

practices reduced the time to 50% flowering by 6 and 9 d in the wet and dry seasons, respectively, since the seedlings did not suffer from transplanting shock as in transplanting and seedling throwing. Santhi et al (1998) reported similar benefits of direct seeding over transplanting.

Thus, direct (wet) seeding, preferably through the drum seeder, could be recommended wherever labor is scarce and costly. In this way, farmers could obtain higher net incomes besides shortening the field-use duration in lowland irrigated rice.

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Influence of seedling age and number of seedlings on yield attributes and yield of hybrid rice in the wet season

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In the irrigated rice ecosystem that uses high-yielding varieties (HYVs), yields have already started plateauing. In India, where it is not possible to put more area into rice cultivation, adopting hybrids with suitable management practices would certainly be an alternative for increasing rice productivity. A study conducted at the C Block Seed Farm of BCKV during the 1998 and 1999 wet seasons examined the performance of hybrids as well as HYVs with different seedling ages and seedling number hill⁻¹.

The field was sandy loam to clay loam with a neutral soil reaction. Seeds were collected from the Rice Research Station in

Chinsurah. Treatments consisted of two hybrid rice cultivars (Pro-Agro 6201 and CNRH 3) and one HYV (IET4786), two seedling ages (21 and 28 d), and two levels of seedling number hill⁻¹ (1 and 2 seedlings hill⁻¹ for hybrid rice and 3 and 6 seedlings hill⁻¹ for the HYV). The crop was transplanted in the last week of July for both seasons using the rectangular planting method. The spacing was 20 cm × 10 cm. A dose of 80 kg N, 17.6 kg P, and 33.2 kg K ha⁻¹ was applied under recommended practices of split doses of N and K. The experiment was laid out in a factorial randomized block design with three replications. Results revealed that Pro-Agro 6201 gave a significantly higher yield

than IET4786, not only because of more mature panicles m⁻² but also because of a higher number of filled grains panicle⁻¹ and greater seed weight. Pro-Agro 6201 showed a more profuse tillering habit at an early stage than the HYV, which could be due to hybrid vigor (heterosis). Twenty-eight-day-old seedlings produced more tillers, panicles m⁻², and grain yield than did 21-d-old seedlings, which performed poorly because of insufficient growth at earlier stages. Seedlings hill⁻¹ significantly influenced number of tillers and mature panicles m⁻² and, consequently, rice yield. Two seedlings hill⁻¹ gave a significantly higher yield than one seedling, along with